

Sustainable leadership and public schools district supervisors' performance: Basis for enhancement program

Bernie L. Libo-on¹, Citrobelle A. Aldeguer²

¹Assistant Schools Division Superintendent/Schools Division of Sipalay City/Institution/ University of St. La Salle
Bacolod City, Philippines

²Education Program Supervisor/Schools Division of La Carlota City/ University of St. La Salle
Bacolod City, Philippines

Corresponding email: citrobelle.aldeguer@deped.gov.ph

ABSTRACT

In order to assess the degree of sustainable leadership components—such as creating a vision and setting direction, getting to know and support peers, overseeing the teaching and learning program, and restructuring the way the 32 public schools district supervisors (PSDS) in the Division of Negros Occidental are organized—this study used a descriptive research design. The majority of the participants were 47 years old and below and mostly were female with master's degree holders, also were 14 years and below as PSDS almost were married, and with low monthly income. The profile of the participants implies that the variables of age, gender, civil status, and monthly income are not factors or characteristics to influence the sustainable leadership of public schools district supervisors. Therefore, these factors have no bearing on the public school district supervisors' dedication to carrying out their roles. With the exception of high-level responses on the indicators, where PSDS made sure that appropriate support, like professional development, teaching materials, and planning time, was provided when they were classified according to age, sex, highest educational attainment, length of service, civil status, and monthly income, there was a very high level of building the vision and setting direction, redesigning the organization, understanding, and developing peers in this context. In order to improve the program even further, we close with a prediction regarding the future directions of sustainable leadership research.

ARTICLE INFO

Received : May 14, 2024

Revised : Jun. 2, 2024

Accepted : Jun. 28, 2024

KEYWORDS

*Building the vision,
Developing peers, Managing
the teaching and learning
program, Redesigning the
organization, Setting
direction, Understanding,
Sustainable leadership*

Suggested Citation (APA Style 7th Edition):

Libo-on, B.L. & Aldeguer, C.A. (2024). Sustainable leadership and public schools district supervisors' performance: Basis for enhancement program. *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 4(2), 75-87. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730319>

INTRODUCTION

There is a clear mandate for school leaders to do more to ensure their schools' leadership sustainability. In a world where societal values are changing, it is necessary to ensure its continued relevance. The relationship between operational sustainability practices and the educational system as a whole is a crucial question for school leaders. If major constituencies are beginning to place more emphasis on sustainable leadership practices, how should the organization position and communicate these practices? Obtaining unbiased observations about the part sustainability practices play in important stakeholder groups' decision-making processes is essential to provide an answer to this topic. School administrators can use data, not guesswork, to determine the order of importance of sustainability projects by measuring them properly. At its best, sustainable leadership is not a carousel of administrators moving in and out of positions. Educators need to be able to lean on their administration in the fact that their principals are present, easy to approach, willing to listen, and capable of supporting their teachers with whatever they may need (Passinger, 2022). Cognizant of the foregoing concepts and discussions, the researcher as a public school district supervisor finds importance in determining and emphasizing the significant impact of sustainable leadership on the public school district supervisors' performance in the Division of Negros Occidental. Public Schools District Supervisors face numerous challenges in their roles, especially when it comes to maintaining sustainable leadership. One of the components of effective management and supervision of schools, reports, and accomplishments could be challenges. The researcher believes that to achieve the objectives of providing outstanding sustainable leadership, he should continuously effort to promote the professional growth of school leaders and improve teachers' performance and students' learning. It is from the foregoing concepts that this study was conducted.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the sustainable leadership and public schools district supervisors' performance in the Division of Negros Occidental.

1. What is the profile of public schools district supervisors in terms of the following selected variables: age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, civil status, and average monthly income?
2. What is the level of sustainable leadership of public schools district supervisors when grouped according to the aforementioned variables and in terms of the following components: building a vision and setting direction, understanding and developing peers, managing the teaching and learning program, and redesigning the organization?
3. What is the level of public schools district supervisors' performance in the Division of Negros Occidental when they are grouped according to the aforementioned grouping variables?
4. From the findings of the study, what enhancement program should be designed to improve the sustainable leadership and the public schools district supervisors' performance in the Division of Negros Occidental?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the performance of public schools district supervisors in the Division of Negros Occidental and to ascertain sustainable leadership. A descriptive research approach was used to achieve this goal. The participants of the study were the 32 public school district supervisors in the Division of Negros Occidental. The participants assessed their level of sustainable leadership in their respective districts. The questionnaire was adapted from the work of Hardie (2011); however, certain revisions were done to suit the needs of the present study since Hardie's study used the teachers as participants while the present study utilized the public schools district supervisors as participants.

The following criteria were used to evaluate the public school district supervisors' performance and degree of sustainable leadership: (a) creating a vision and establishing direction; (b) getting to know and support peers; (c) overseeing the curriculum and instruction; and (d) restructuring the organization.

The data in this study were entered into the data matrix using Microsoft Excel. Then, the data were transported to the Statistical Program for Social Sciences (SPSS); to determine the profile of the public schools district supervisors in terms of selected variables, the frequency and percentage were used; to determine the level of sustainable leadership of the public school's district supervisors, the mean was used; and on the level of public schools district supervisors' performance, the mean was used.

On the Sustainable Leadership

The fundamental elements that support the school's longer-term development make up sustainable leadership. It creates a leadership culture with a moral foundation that makes success attainable for everyone (Leithwood et al. 2008). Hargreaves and Fink (2006) state that it is applicable to every area of the organization's operations. The essence of sustainable leadership may be summed up as follows: it ensures a positive influence on all that surrounds us now and in the future while preserving and expanding our knowledge of anything that spreads and endures without causing harm. A personal contribution, or the alteration of each participant's perspective, is necessary for sustainable action.

As a result, the development of self-awareness begins at the individual level and progresses to the group, organizational, and societal levels. Not only some pupils at the expense of others but all students and institutions gain from sustainable leadership. Sustainable leadership recognizes the tendency of leaders at lighthouse, magnet, or charter schools to marginalize others and the temptation that wealthy communities may have to pick the best members of the local leadership corps. The practice of sustainable leadership is a multifaceted one. It acknowledges and owns up to the fact that schools are interconnected in complex webs of influence.

Accordingly, concerns of social justice are closely linked to sustainability and succession (Baker and Foote, 2010). Brown (2005) delves even further into the topic of leadership for sustainability. He investigated the engagement of highly skilled sustainability leaders in sustainability programs. Brown developed several qualities for sustainable leadership based on interviews with a small sample of these leaders. The competencies are linked to the capacity to respect and establish a close connection with the work of sustainability as a holy expression and a spiritual practice. Leadership focused on sustainability sees sustainability work as a means of transforming oneself, other people, and the globe.

Numerous scholars have concurred that literacy and numeracy instruction should take precedence in the early stages of school reform initiatives. According to Davies and Davies (2006), selecting which outside initiatives to deploy to support the schools' improvement agenda would need a significant amount of talent. Hopkins (2001) stated that a new initiative's ability to enhance student learning is a necessary component for consideration at all times. If an effort is not in line with the school's goal, instructors will become overworked and dispersed.

Lateral capacity building, according to Hargreaves and Fink (2006) and Fullan (2005), would promote care for the leader's school as well as other schools in the community. Leithwood and Mascal (2008) found that leadership influence had a greater effect on teacher motivation and work environment than on capacity. It was stated that there is a notable difference in student accomplishment among schools that can be explained by collective leadership. They did, however, voice some reservations regarding the current wave of widespread support for distributed leadership as a result of their preliminary findings.

Day (2007) emphasized that equity, well-being, and positive personal and societal outcomes are all important aspects of success that go beyond test scores. Furthermore, even if they are challenging to assess, a love of learning, critical thinking abilities, and problem-solving techniques must be taught in our classrooms, according to Hargreaves and Fink (2006) and Davies (2007). In order to act in the best interests of their pupils, educators must consider the goal of education and work to create a shared understanding of what is important. This necessitates that educators carefully consider the lessons pupils should learn as well as the instructional strategies that will support their learning. Encouraging every student to succeed in their studies is the aim. The principal's job is to offer the direction and guidance necessary to make sure this happens.

Teachers view the principal's leadership as the primary factor supporting their school's enhanced or sustained effectiveness and improvement, according to Day, Leithwood, and Sammons (2008). Leithwood and Riehl (2003) noted that the principle has a significant indirect impact on students' learning. The most potent and indirect means by which school leaders enhance teaching and learning are through their impact on employee commitment, motivation, and working environment.

Leithwood and Mascall (2008) established that teacher motivation and work setting were more susceptible to leadership influence than capacity. They argued collective leadership does explain significant variation in student achievement across schools. However, their provisional insights led them to express some concerns about the present overwhelming support for distributed leadership. Leithwood and Mascall saw limited evidence that parents or students had much influence. In addition, teachers perceived influence to be exercised in their schools in a distributed but still hierarchical manner. They believed further research was necessary to better understand distributed leadership and to make decisions about its application in schools.

Leithwood and Mascall declared that there is no empirical justification for advocating a more playful distribution of leadership as a strategy of organizational improvement beyond those important efforts to enlist the full range of capacities and commitments found within school organizations. Leithwood and Mascall acknowledged using a unidimensional measure of leadership, limited to influence on decision-making that may have greatly impacted their findings. Developing leadership in others is a critical component of sustainable leadership for school improvement.

The Components of the Sustainable Leadership

Fink et al. (2010) said that there are very few examples in the literature if the objective is continuous development in deep learning over protracted periods of time for all children. Still, there is a lot of research in the field of sustainable leadership that supports what Morgan (2007) referred to as an emphasis on shared meanings and cooperative action. Organizational leaders are faced with a constant stream of new challenges that require creative solutions. These challenges include managing an organization, communicating and planning for future organizational activities, preparing for rapid changes, labor diversity, global competition, shifting market conditions, and changing organizational culture.

Similar to this, a leader who wants to maintain their position of authority within an organization should begin by evaluating their own traits and competencies. If they find areas where they fall short, they should then continuously improve so that they may lead by example and encourage their team members to apply creativity and innovation (Brown, 2005). In comparison to earlier decades, the kind of school leadership needed in today's schools is significantly different and more intricate. The role of a school administrator is difficult and complex, and it gets harder every year. In addition to collaborating closely with educators, parents, and students, principals are supposed to act as a catalyst for the growth of leadership abilities across the board. According to Mulford and Silins (2003), there needs to be a significant shift that includes the provision of sustainable leadership.

Additionally, for more than ten years, improving schools has been a top priority in education. While there have been clear areas of accomplishment, there hasn't been much continuous progress. In order to bring about change in schools, charismatic school-based leaders have collaborated with teachers; some have even been effective in achieving immediate improvements. Unfortunately, evidence indicates that success generally ends when the administrator departs the school, making this success elusive (Davies, 2007). According to Polman (2009), the art of leadership involves facing reality head-on.

Various sub-disciplines of Sustainable Leadership provide intriguing leadership competencies. Compared to earlier decades, the kind of school leadership needed in schools now is significantly different and more intricate. The role of a school administrator is difficult and complex, and it gets harder every year. In addition to collaborating closely with educators, parents, and students, principals are supposed to act as a catalyst for the growth of leadership

abilities across the board. According to Mulford and Silins (2003), there needs to be a significant shift that includes the provision of sustainable leadership.

For more than ten years, improving schools has been a top priority in education. While there have been clear areas of accomplishment, there hasn't been much continuous progress. In order to bring about change in schools, charismatic school-based leaders have collaborated with teachers; some have even been effective in achieving immediate improvements. Unfortunately, evidence indicates that success generally ends when the administrator departs the school, making this success elusive (Davies, 2007).

The general public's need for educational equity has grown. Governments have implemented a number of compulsory reforms after realizing this requirement. Even if educational attainment has improved, it has typically plateaued below the intended level despite these efforts. Studies have focused on sustainable leadership, which is seen by many as the secret to long-term educational progress. The objective is large-scale educational development where gains can be more durable and form the foundation for further improvements (Fullan, 2009).

The researcher gained valuable insights and a comprehensive background for this study, especially about leadership and sustainable leadership, from the reviewed concepts and studies. Without capable and capable leaders to steer their organizations, schools could not continue to exist or elevate in the community. The most valuable resource in industrialized nations and the most critical one in developing ones is effective leadership. Thus, much like in the case of the educational system, leadership is essential to the development of an institution. For more than ten years, improving schools has been a top priority in education. While there have been clear areas of accomplishment, there hasn't been much continuous progress. To bring about change in schools, charismatic school-based leaders have collaborated with teachers; some have even been effective in achieving immediate improvements. Unfortunately, evidence indicates that success generally ends when the administrator departs the school, making this success elusive (Davies, 2007).

The general public's need for educational equity has grown. Governments have implemented many compulsory reforms after realizing this requirement. Even if educational attainment has improved, it has typically plateaued below the intended level in spite of these efforts. Studies have focused on sustainable leadership, which is seen by many as the secret to long-term educational progress. The objective is large-scale educational development where gains can be more durable and form the foundation for further improvements (Fullan, 2009).

In Hargreaves' 2009 report, "On the Education Change," four main areas of change were highlighted along with a comprehensive reform strategy. The first approach, which was optimistic and innovative, was when educators used their judgment and small-scale innovation emerged but did not take off. Studies on school effectiveness began to appear during this time, and school growth progressively came into focus. According to Hargreaves, the second approach is when parental choice, performance targets, goals, and capacity building become prevalent, leading to a complex and contradictory situation.

Likewise, the third approach which includes standardization and marketization brings top-down performance targets while also emphasizing the value of peer networking and capacity building. The fourth approach has increased public and professional involvement along with government expectations. Hargreaves thought that this was the time to usher in an era of inspiration and sustainability in education.

Furthermore, according to Polman (2009) in *The Art of Leadership*, effective leadership involves facing reality head-on. According to him, sustainability leaders typically have a strong role to play in defining, promoting, and defending a significant overarching purpose of corporate activity—one that elevates those who serve it, inspires personal commitment, and unites people to take coordinated action. According to Immelt (2007), it entails granting independence within predetermined bounds, such as dedication, passion, trust, and cooperation. There's lots of leeway within those bounds. However, none can pass over those four barriers. Leaders in sustainability enhance expertise and abilities while offering chances and materials for suitable action.

According to Greenleaf (2002), the servant-leader comes first. The innate desire to serve is where it all starts. The desire to lead is then brought about by conscious choice. He agrees that the human element of change is crucial. Leadership Objectives: Education leaders aspire to leave a lasting legacy, accomplish meaningful goals, and motivate people to work with them toward those objectives. Establishing learning that engages students intellectually, socially, and emotionally is the primary duty of all education leaders.

According to Glickman (2008), sustainable leadership aims to produce long-lasting, significant advances in learning rather than just short-term increases in test scores. Leaders must give leadership succession careful consideration if they want to practice sustainable leadership. This objective can be met by preparing successors to carry out significant reforms, retaining effective leaders in schools longer when they are significantly advancing student learning, resisting the need to look for irreplaceable, charismatic heroes to save education, mandating the inclusion of succession plans in all district and school improvement plans, and decreasing the frequency of successive successions to prevent teachers from cynically choosing to "wait out" all of their leaders (Fink & Brayman, 2006).

Encouraging others to share and contribute to the development of one's vision is one approach for leaders to leave a lasting legacy. Thus, leadership succession entails more than just developing the next principal. It entails sharing leadership among the professional community of the school so that others can take up the mantle after the principal retires (Spillane, Halverson, & Drummond, 2001).

Hargreaves and Fink (2004) consider diversity as important in sustainable leadership and argue that productive diversity requires less, rather than more testing, greater curriculum flexibility, and creativity. Diversity also helps with the knowledge and learning needs of culturally diverse communities and personalized learning. These researchers say sustainable leadership builds on the past in its quest to create a better future. They refer to the protection of the natural environment and consider 'learning to live sustainably' as an added principle of learning.

On the other hand, some of the procedures required for leadership succession include task and objective assignment, shadowing, mentoring, coaching, and exposure to all facets of the role. According to Davies (2007), leaders who believe they are the only ones responsible for an organization's success frequently depart without competent leaders to take their place.

An essential component of an organization's long-term survival is leadership succession. Hargreaves and Fink (2006) assert in their book *Sustainable Leadership* that managing leadership transition is crucial to guaranteeing the long-term viability of improvement initiatives. Various sub-disciplines of Sustainable Leadership provide intriguing leadership competencies. Effective leaders are essential to the educational system to maximize student progress. School administrators are mostly responsible for making these academic gains a reality by providing direction and inspiration to their staff members to complete their jobs.

Because it might affect subordinates' impressions of completing and executing their tasks efficiently, school administrators must possess sustainable leadership that would match the expectations of teachers and the community at large. Positive reinforcement from sustainable leadership broadens the perspective of subordinates' contributions, which in turn affects how well they accomplish their jobs. In addition, the responsibility of sustainable leadership is to motivate followers to pursue specific goals. It conjures up ideas and motivates people to realize them and push themselves over their comfort zones.

One of the first people to advocate for this type of leadership in education, Fullan (2009), put up several compelling and distinctive sustainable leadership ideas. Sustainable leadership, in his view, entails succession planning and preparation from the moment a leader is appointed, not later. Thus, sustainable leadership involves more than just keeping up academic progress in one's institution. Concerned about sustainability, leaders take ownership of the schools and children they impact in the larger environment.

Because of this, leaders may guarantee that their legacy is shared and developed in concert with others in order to leave a lasting impact. Thus, leadership succession entails more than just developing the heirs to the chief position. According to Spillane, Halverson, and Drummond (2001), it entails sharing leadership across the school's professional community so that they can continue the principal's legacy and lessen the impact of the principal succession.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 showed the profile of the public schools district supervisors in the Division of Negros Occidental. Generally, the entire group of participants was composed of 32 (100.00%) who served as participants in the study. The entire group of the study was composed of 32 public schools district supervisors who served as participants in the study. When grouped according to age, many of the participants were young. Usually, school districts draft complex plans for supervision intending to have supervisors assess subordinates for improved performance. Instructors receive monetary rewards for attending a wide range of workshops or pursuing arbitrary graduate courses at different institutions and universities. Despite strong evidence that these conventional approaches have minimal effect on teaching quality, districts have stuck with them. Moreover, this method is predicated on the idea that enhancing a single teacher's efficiency will enhance the organization as a whole. Put an excellent individual in a lousy system, and the system will always prevail, as W. Edwards Deming said (Hattie, 2009).

When the participants were categorized by gender, most of them were female. Master's degree holders make up most participants when categorized by the highest level of education. When grouped according to length of service, many of the participants had a shorter length of service. When grouped according to civil status, many of the participants were married. Lastly, most of the participants had a low or average monthly income.

Table 1. Profile of Public Schools District Supervisor in the Division of Negros Occidental

Grouping Variables	(f)	(%)
A. Entire Group	32	100.00%
B. Age		
Younger (47 Years Old and Below)	22	68.80
Older (48 Years Old and Above)	10	31.30
C. Sex		
Male	13	40.60
Female	19	59.40
D. Highest Educational Attainment		
Master's Degree (M.A., M.A.Ed., MS, etc.)	21	65.60
Doctor of Philosophy (Ed. D. and PhD etc.)	11	34.40
E. Length of Service		
Shorter (14 Years and Below)	19	59.40
Longer (15 Years and Above)	13	40.60
F. Civil Status		
Married	27	84.40
Single	5	15.60
G. Average Monthly Income		
Low (P40,000.00 - P46, 000.00)	19	59.40
Average (P46,000.01 - P52,000.00)	7	21.90
High (P52,000.01 - P58,000.00)	6	18.80

Table 9 presents a summary of public schools district supervisors' vision-setting and building level when categorized based on various grouping characteristics, as indicated in Table 2. The group of supervisors of public schools districts received a mean score of 4.71 when analyzed as a whole, indicating a typically high degree of vision-setting and building.

Table 2: An overview of the public schools district supervisors' level of vision-building and direction-setting when grouped based on the previously indicated grouping variables

Grouping Variables	Mean (\bar{X})	Interpretation
A. Entire Group	4.71	VHL
B. Age		
Younger (47 Years Old and Below)	4.67	VHL
Older (48 Years Old and Above)	4.79	VHL
C. Sex		
Male	4.63	VHL
Female	4.77	VHL
D. Highest Educational Attainment		
Master's Degree (M.A., M.A.Ed., MS etc.)	4.64	VHL
Doctor of Philosophy (Ed. D. and PhD etc.)	4.84	VHL
E. Length of Service		
Shorter (14 Years and Below)	4.72	VHL
Longer (15 Years and Above)	4.69	VHL
F. Civil Status		
Married	4.72	VHL
Single	4.65	VHL
G. Average Monthly Income		
Low (P40,000.00 - P46, 000.00)	4.70	VHL
Average (P46,000.01 - P52,000.00)	4.66	VHL
High (P52,000.01 - P58,000.00)	4.77	VHL

Legend: VHL-Very High Level, HL-High Level, ML-Moderate Level, LL-Low Level, VL-Very Low Level

As shown in Table 3, the summary on the level of understanding and developing peer of public schools district supervisors when they were classified as to the aforementioned grouping variables appeared in Table 16. When public schools district supervisors were taken as a whole, it obtained the mean score of = 4.56 and was generally rated as a “very high” level in understanding and developing peers.

Table 3: Summary on the Level of Understanding and Developing Peer of Public Schools District Supervisors When Group According to Aforementioned Grouping Variables

Grouping Variables	Mean (\bar{X})	Interpretation
A. Entire Group	4.56	VHL
B. Age		
Younger (47 Years Old and Below)	4.59	VHL
Older (48 Years Old and Above)	4.51	VHL
C. Sex		
Male	4.54	VHL
Female	4.58	VHL

D. Highest Educational Attainment		
Master’s Degree (M.A., M.A.Ed., MS etc.)	4.54	<i>VHL</i>
Doctor of Philosophy (Ed. D. and PhD etc.)	4.61	<i>VHL</i>
E. Length of Service		
Shorter (14 Years and Below)	4.58	<i>VHL</i>
Longer (15 Years and Above)	4.54	<i>VHL</i>
F. Civil Status		
Married	4.56	<i>VHL</i>
Single	4.60	<i>VHL</i>
G. Average Monthly Income		
Low (P40,000.00 - P46, 000.00)	4.56	<i>VHL</i>
Average (P46,000.01 - P52,000.00)	4.59	<i>VHL</i>
High (P52,000.01 - P58,000.00)	4.54	<i>VHL</i>

Legend: VHL-Very High Level, HL-High Level, ML-Moderate Level, LL-Low Level, VL-Very Low Level

As shown in Table 4, presented the summary of the level of managing the teaching and learning program of public schools district supervisors when grouped according to the aforementioned grouping variables. The entire group of participants of the study obtained a mean score of = 4.71 and was generally evaluated as a “very high” level in managing the teaching and learning program. When they were classified into age, the younger public schools district supervisors (47 years old and below) exhibited a very high level of managing the teaching and learning program with a mean score of = 4.70, while the older ones (48 years old and above) had a very high level of managing the teaching and learning program with a mean score of =4.71.

Table 4: Summary on the Level of Managing the Teaching and Learning Program of Public Schools District Supervisors When Group According to Aforementioned Grouping Variables

Grouping Variables	Mean (\bar{X})	Interpretation
A. Entire Group	4.71	<i>VHL</i>
B. Age		
Younger (47 Years Old and Below)	4.70	<i>VHL</i>
Older (48 Years Old and Above)	4.71	<i>VHL</i>
C. Sex		
Male	4.69	<i>VHL</i>
Female	4.71	<i>VHL</i>
D. Highest Educational Attainment		
Master’s Degree (M.A., M.A.Ed., MS etc.)	4.66	<i>VHL</i>
Doctor of Philosophy (Ed. D. and PhD etc.)	4.79	<i>VHL</i>
E. Length of Service		
Shorter (14 Years and Below)	4.73	<i>VHL</i>
Longer (15 Years and Above)	4.67	<i>VHL</i>
F. Civil Status		
Married	4.70	<i>VHL</i>
Single	4.71	<i>VHL</i>
G. Average Monthly Income		
Low (P40,000.00 - P46, 000.00)	4.71	<i>VHL</i>
Average (P46,000.01 - P52,000.00)	4.65	<i>VHL</i>
High (P52,000.01 - P58,000.00)	4.74	<i>VHL</i>

Legend: VHL-Very High Level, HL-High Level, ML-Moderate Level, LL-Low Level, VL-Very Low Level

Table 5 shows the summary on the level of redesigning the organization of public schools district supervisors when grouped according to the aforementioned grouping variables. Most of the public schools district supervisors’ level of redesigning organization when they were classified as to highest educational attainment, public schools

district supervisors with master’s degree holder had a very high level of redesigning the organization with a mean score of = 4.59, while public schools district supervisors with doctorate degree holder had a very high level of redesigning the organization with a mean score of = 4.61.

Table 5: Summary on the Level of Redesigning the Organization of Public Schools District Supervisors When Grouped According to Aforementioned Grouping Variables

Grouping Variables	Mean (\bar{X})	Interpretation
A. Entire Group	4.60	VHL
B. Age		
Younger (47 Years Old and Below)	4.66	VHL
Older (48 Years Old and Above)	4.47	HL
C. Sex		
Male	4.57	VHL
Female	4.62	VHL
D. Highest Educational Attainment		
Master’s Degree (M.A., M.A.Ed., MS etc.)	4.59	VHL
Doctor of Philosophy (Ed. D. and PhD etc.)	4.61	VHL
E. Length of Service		
Shorter (14 Years and Below)	4.65	VHL
Longer (15 Years and Above)	4.53	VHL
F. Civil Status		
Married	4.58	VHL
Single	4.69	VHL
G. Average Monthly Income		
Low (P40,000.00 - P46, 000.00)	4.59	VHL
Average (P46,000.01 - P52,000.00)	4.61	VHL
High (P52,000.01 - P58,000.00)	4.60	VHL

Legend: VHL-Very High Level, HL-High Level, ML-Moderate Level, LL-Low Level, VL-Very Low Level

While on the level of individual performance commitment review form of public schools district supervisors in the Division of Negros Occidental when grouped according to the aforementioned variables was reflected in Table 32. Most of the public schools district supervisors had a “high” level of performance with a mean score of = 4.40. When they were classified as to age, younger (47 years old and below) public schools district supervisors had a “high” level of performance with a mean score of = 4.41, while older (48 years old and above) public schools district supervisors had a “high” level of performance with a mean score of = 4.37.

Table 6: The Level of Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) of Public Schools District Supervisors in the Division of Negros Occidental When Grouped According to Aforementioned Grouping Variables

Grouping Variables	Mean (\bar{X})	Interpretation
A. Entire Group	4.40	HL
B. Age		
Younger (47 Years Old and Below)	4.41	HL
Older (48 Years Old and Above)	4.37	HL
C. Sex		
Male	4.42	HL
Female	4.38	HL
D. Highest Educational Attainment		
Master’s Degree (M.A., M.A.Ed., MS etc.)	4.36	HL
Doctor of Philosophy (Ed. D. and PhD etc.)	4.46	HL

E. Length of Service		
Shorter (14 Years and Below)	4.42	<i>HL</i>
Longer (15 Years and Above)	4.36	<i>HL</i>
F. Civil Status		
Married	4.39	<i>HL</i>
Single	4.41	<i>HL</i>
G. Average Monthly Income		
Low (P40,000.00 - P46, 000.00)	4.33	<i>HL</i>
Average (P46,000.01 - P52,000.00)	4.45	<i>HL</i>
High (P52,000.01 - P58,000.00)	4.53	<i>VHL</i>

VHL - Very High Level, *HL* - High Level, *ML* - Moderate Level, *LL* - Low Level, *VLL* - Very Low Level

The myriad of one-size-fits-all mandates being forced to endure in public education has, in many places, created a culture by default. This default culture has focused on following plans to satisfy mandates, it has focused on performance on standardized assessments, and it has focused on meeting the minimum. In short, the current educational system has taken the wind from the sails; it has taken the passion out of teaching. Hence, school leaders must empower teachers to be passionate about teaching. Values and educational foundations must be defined. A culture of personalization—both for teachers and students should be established; and trust, value, talent, and dedication of the teachers in classrooms must be adhered to. It is believed that skilled and passionate school leadership is the key to educational equality and school transformation. Transforming school leadership is one of the key reform strategies that help deliver the school’s mission to prepare every child for academic endeavours.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study comprised thirty-two public school district supervisors who participated in the study as a whole. When the participants were sorted by age, most of them were young. When the participants were categorized by gender, most of them were female. Master's degree holders make up the majority of participants when categorized by the highest level of education. The majority of the participants had a shorter length of service. When grouped according to civil status, the majority of the participants were married. Lastly, the majority of the participants had a low or average monthly income. This implies that the variables of age, gender, civil status, and monthly income are not factors or characteristics to influence the sustainable leadership of public school district supervisors. The dedication of the public school district supervisors to carrying out their roles and obligations is unaffected by these factors. As a result, individuals can give their utmost effort despite the previously listed factors. On the other hand, the length of service and educational background of public school district supervisors are important elements that influence and support their practice of sustainable leadership. This essentially indicates that a public school district supervisor's dedication to practicing sustainable leadership is correlated with his level of education and duration of service, as well as with his accumulation of knowledge and work experience.

When categorized by age, sex, highest educational attainment, length of service, civil status, and monthly income, the participants demonstrated a "very high" level of sustainable leadership among public school district supervisors. They also demonstrated a high level of understanding and developing peers, managing the teaching and learning program, and redesigning the organization. In conclusion, when the participants were categorized based on the previously established grouping characteristics, they demonstrated a "very high" degree of sustainable leadership and performance. This suggests that the supervisors of public schools districts are totally dedicated to carrying out their roles and obligations in accordance with the expectations placed on them. This simply indicates that the exceptional performance of the district is directly related to and seen as the result of the public schools district supervisors' commitment and dedication to carrying out their roles and responsibilities as well as their practice of sustainable leadership.

When the public schools district supervisors in the Division of Negros Occidental were categorized based on the previously mentioned variables, their performance level was found to be "very high." This was the case when the supervisors were categorized based on age, sex, highest educational attainment, length of service, civil status, and

monthly income. According to the outcome of their Individual Performance Review and Commitment Form grade, public schools district supervisors have been performing exceptionally well in their field or district.

The findings of the study showed that sustainable leadership was practiced by the public schools district supervisors to a very high or optimum level. It is recommended that the findings of the study be revealed to them considering such concern was assessed by them, hence they could assess whether or not the results of the study are truly reflective of their leadership performance.

To the DepEd Officials. To achieve the goals of leadership sustainability, they should take the required corrective actions, such as providing facilities, suitable teaching materials, and sufficient financing. It is also advised that school administrators who perform exceptionally well in their leadership roles receive the proper recognition to increase their motivation to perform and serve as role models for other stakeholders.

To the Public Schools District Supervisors. They should routinely get capacity building through workshops, seminars, and the like to increase their competence, proficiency, and effectiveness in carrying out their duties that will benefit the students. Through these kinds of activities, students will acquire information and skills that will enable them to effectively and efficiently convey knowledge to the beneficiaries. Supervisors of public schools districts should create a climate that is encouraging and helpful and share accountability for creating lifelong learners with the community and other stakeholders.

To the School Administrators and Teachers. They should engage in, support, and collaborate with the school's leadership and related issues under the direction of the public school district supervisors to cultivate stronger leader-follower relationships, which could further improve services to the school's clientele.

To the Parents. As an internal stakeholder in the school, especially about the academic and social development of the students, they may be able to support the establishment of trust and confidence in the school administration where their children are enrolled to foster cordial relationships and, as a result, accomplish school goals and objectives.

To the Pupils. Since students are at the core of the educational process, improved school administration can offer them high-quality instruction that will inspire and motivate them to complete their assignments and develop into useful, productive people.

To the Future Researchers. They might carry out more studies in this area. Such research ought to take into account other facets or domains of the subject matter that are not addressed in the current study investigation, such as the examination of intervening variables that could impact or affect leadership performance and sustainability.

REFERENCES

- Brown, K.M. (2005). Pivotal points. In F. W. Fenwick (Ed.), *The Sage Handbook of educational leadership: Advances in theory, research, and practice* (pp. 109–137). Sage.
- Davies, B.J., & Davies, B. (2006). Developing a model for strategic leadership in schools. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 34(1), 121–139.
- Davies, B. (2007). *Developing sustainable leadership*. Paul Chapman.
- Fink, D. & Brayman, C. (2006). School leadership succession and the challenges of change. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 42(1), 62–89.
- Hardie, R.A. (2011). *Principals perception of the essential components of sustainable leadership and implication for succession planning at the elementary school level: A mixed methods research study*.
- Hargreaves, A. & Fink, D. (2006). *Sustainable learning*. Jossey Bass.

- Hopkins, D. (2001). *School improvement for real*. RoutledgeFalmer.
- Leithwood, K., & Mascall, B. (2008). Collective leadership effects on students achievement. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 44(4), 529–561.
- Morgan, D. (2007). Paradigms lost and pragmatism regained: Methodological implication of combining qualitative and quantitative methods. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(1), 48–76.
- Mulford, B., & Silins, H. (2003). Leadership for organizational learning and improved student outcomes—What do we know? *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 33(2), 175–195.
- Polman, P. (2009). McKinsey conversations with global leaders: Paul Polman of Unilever. *McKinsey Quarterly*, October.
- Quinn, L., & Norton, J. (2004). *Beyond*.
- Stoll, L., & Fink, D. (1996). *Changing our schools: Linking school effectiveness and school improvement*. Open University Press.
- Passinger, A. (2022). How sustainable leadership can create thriving schools.